

Flame Monitoring System Based on Images for Steel Reheating Furnaces: a Case Study of Validation from Laboratory to Semi-Industrial Scales

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ABSTRACT

The steel industry is searching for novel image systems to monitor multiple burners individually. Such a development is highly complex and requires studies on several scales. This work analyses the robustness of an imaging system in different scenarios, from the laboratory (design and development) and semi-industrial (implementation) stages, using 20 kW and 1.2 MW burners, respectively. The monitoring system predicts oxygen concentration in flue gases on both scales, achieving accuracies higher than 0.95 in most cases and 0.79 as a minimum. The vision system detects slight variations in combustion conditions and addresses differences among development phases, including burner typologies and system placements. This study leads flame monitoring systems based on images toward their final development on an industrial scale.

KEYWORDS

Flame monitoring, system validation, computer vision, machine learning, steel reheating furnace, blast furnace gas

INTRODUCTION

Energy-intensive industries continue searching for alternatives to increase their efficiency and sustainability. The steel industry demands high-temperature processes, mainly by the combustion of solid, liquid, or gaseous fuels. Monitoring systems can enhance the control and performance of such combustion processes, reducing fuel consumption, emissions, and costs, to reach European targets for carbon emissions by 2030.

Industrial furnaces are usually equipped with several groups of burners, and the furnace operation is evaluated by analysing global combustion parameters. Monitoring air-fuel flows and flue gas emissions for each burner could detect individual malfunctions to raise the efficiency of the process. Still, this alternative is not feasible by the high cost of individual monitoring with traditional sensors. Thus, novel systems are searched to monitor multiple burners individually. In this context, image systems equipped with computer vision and

Machine Learning (ML) systems have a high potential, enabling the supervision of several burners by a single camera.

Cameras can be employed to evaluate the combustion [1] and compute quantitative characteristics such as the flame area [2]. These systems can be developed to predict the equivalence ratio [3] or different combustion conditions [4]. Computer vision algorithms usually use flame segmentation to compute image features from only flame pixels. However, flame segmentation could be complex or inaccurate for images without a clear flame body. Another alternative is the analysis of flame images without performing flame segmentation, extracting features for the whole image [5, 6]. Typical image features can be split into statistical, textural, and geometrical. Statistical and textural features can be extracted from images with and without flame segmentation. Nevertheless, geometrical features need flame segmentation to define the flame body and compute characteristics such as the flame length.

Developing advanced image systems for industrial scale is challenging and needs studies at several scales. However, most research works in the open literature focus on a single scale, usually the laboratory scale. This work presents the validation or joint assessment for laboratory and semi-industrial scales of an advanced image system that automatically predicts oxygen (O_2) concentration in flue gases using an image sensor. The two-scale validation is a novelty concerning previous works focused on a single scale, enhancing the insight into sensitivity to changes and robustness of image systems for combustion monitoring. In this aspect, the system's image sensor, image processing, and predictive model were evaluated in different scenarios by comparing design, simulation, and implementation results. A combustion chamber with a 20-kW burner was used for the laboratory scale, while a 1.2 MW burner was employed for the semi-industrial scale furnace. The rated power of the large burner is higher than those used in previous industrial works [7]. Nevertheless, our case was defined as a semi-industrial scale because the furnace has only one burner, whereas, at the industrial scale, the furnace is equipped with multiple burners.

This work is focused on a specific case of the iron and steel industry. This industry is searching for novel systems [8] to individually monitor the multiple burners inside reheating furnaces [9]. Natural Gas (NG) and Blast Furnace Gas (BFG) are usually mixed to provide different fuel blends for these furnaces. The steel industry produces BFG as waste gas that can be valorised as fuel within the same facility [10-12]. Nevertheless, BFG has a low heating value and is prone to combustion instabilities [12, 13]. The temperature in the steel-making processes can be raised by increasing the NG share in the fuel blend with BFG. This strategy is used to meet temperature requirements when needed. In this work, the image system validation was focused on the fuel blends 100 %vol. NG, 30 %vol. NG and 70 %vol. BFG, 20 %vol. NG and 80 %vol. BFG and 100 %vol. BFG.

METHODS

The development stages of the monitoring system were discussed to identify changes in combustion conditions, mainly scales, burners, and camera set-up. Next, monitoring system fundamentals (image sensor, image processing, and predictive models) were assessed in the different development stages, considering condition changes among them. The evaluation procedure is explained as follows.

- Image sensors were assessed by comparing flame images for different combustion conditions. In addition, the simulated and actual views of the furnace were analysed.
- Image processing effectiveness was assessed by analysing relationships between combustion conditions and extracted image features.

- Finally, the performance of predictive models was validated by comparing their accuracy values. Accuracy was defined as the number of correct predictions divided by the total number of predictions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Review of the development

The imaging system was evaluated in different scenarios during its development in order to assess its viability and robustness. Therefore, different scales, burner types, and camera locations were tested, while the imaging system shared several properties during the development stages. This approach differs from the usual validation of a burner, in which the burner typology and characteristics are constant.

A colour camera was employed as the image sensor. The processing algorithm extracted statistical features from the three colour channels of the flame images. In some cases, additional textural and geometrical characteristics were computed. A predictive model was tested to predict O_2 concentration in flue gases for each fuel blend, choosing between three different ML algorithms. A subset of image features was automatically selected to feed the predictive model of each fuel blend. The image sensor, image processing, and predictive model are described in more detail in the next sections. The development stages of the flame monitoring system are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Development stages of the flame monitoring system

Stage	Scale	Burner	Camera placement
Design	Semi-industrial	Diffusion	Outside
Development	Laboratory	Premixed	Outside
Implementation	Semi-industrial	Diffusion	Inside

The first stage included the design requirements for the monitoring system. With that purpose, an experimental campaign was performed at a semi-industrial scale with a diffusion burner of 1.2 MW. This type of burner is characterised by the production of soot and its continuous radiation (black-body emission) [14, 15]. The camera was set outside the furnace, aligned with a viewing port to acquire flame images. The experimental campaign and its results are presented in a previous work [16].

The second phase focused on developing the predictive model with an experimental campaign at the laboratory scale. A combustion chamber with a premixed burner of 20 kW was used in this stage. Premixed burners provide flames that mainly emit several discrete radiations due to chemiluminescence [15, 17]. The camera was placed outside the combustion chamber before an inspection window. The analysis of these image features is included in another work [18].

Lastly, in the implementation stage, a predictive model was developed for the semi-industrial scale performing another experimental campaign. As in the design phase, a diffusion burner of 1.2 MW was employed. However, the camera was set inside the furnace in this case.

Image sensor

Examples of flame images acquired during all the development stages are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Examples of flame images for different O_2 concentrations in flue gases for semi-industrial and laboratory scales, with the fuel blend 70 % vol. BFG and 30 % vol. NG. For the semi-industrial scale, the ((a), (b), and (c)) outside and ((g), (h), and (i)) inside placements of the camera were used, while for laboratory scale, an ((d), (e) and (f)) outside set-up was employed

For the semi-industrial scale, flames had low visibility, but overall image characteristics were affected. For example, the brightness of the images was decreased by raising the O_2 concentration in flue gases with the outside and inside camera locations. At the laboratory scale, images captured a flame body and clear flame front for all combustion conditions. For both diffusion and premixed burners, the images differed depending on the combustion conditions. Therefore, the colour camera was validated as an image sensor for monitoring BFG combustion for diffusion and premixed burners.

At the semi-industrial scale, the burner typology (diffusion) was fixed, but the camera port used to visualize the flame differed. In the design stage, the small size of the viewing port and the outside location affected the camera view, and only part of the furnace inside was captured. For the implementation phase, the captured area of the furnace was maximised by placing the camera inside the furnace. This location was also simulated based on the camera placement and

furnace geometry to check the field of view before the physical setup of the system, as seen in Figure 2. The simulation provided an accurate estimation of the captured area of the furnace.

Figure 2. (a) Simulated and (b) actual views of the inside of the furnace at the semi-industrial scale for the image sensor set-up

Image processing

The same statistical features were extracted from the three colour channels of flame images for all the development stages. Textural and geometrical features were also computed from the three colour channels in some cases (Table 2).

Table 2. Summary of computed image characteristics

Stage	High flame visibility	Statistical features	Textural features	Geometrical features	Total image features
Design	-	Yes	-	-	12
Development	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	66
Implementation	-	Yes	Yes	-	51

First, flame segmentation was only applied to the laboratory scale due to the high visibility of the flame. Therefore, features were computed at the laboratory scale using only flame pixels, while at the semi-industrial scale, all the image pixels were processed. The same statistical features (mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis) were extracted for all the development stages. The textural features computed for laboratory and semi-industrial scales were based on thirteen selected characteristics [19]. The application of flame segmentation at the laboratory scale enabled the use of geometrical features from which flame area, centroid coordinates, width, and height were extracted. All the image features were computed for each colour channel, with 12, 66, and 51 features for each development phase. Figure 3 shows, as an example, the relationship between O_2 concentration in flue gases and the image feature of the red mean for the 70 % vol. BFG/30 % vol. NG fuel blend. This characteristic was selected as an illustrative example since it is extracted in all the development stages.

Figure 3. O₂ concentration in flue gases vs. red mean for semi-industrial and laboratory scales, during the combustion of the fuel blend 70 %vol. BFG and 30 %vol. NG. For the semi-industrial scale, the outside and inside placements of the camera are shown

In all the development stages, image features were affected by the combustion conditions. Statistical and textural features were validated as descriptors of combustion conditions for flames with high and low visibility, respectively.

Predictive model

Predictive models were trained to predict O₂ concentration in flue gases for the laboratory and semi-industrial scales. At the semi-industrial scale, the predictive model was developed only for the inside location of the camera (implementation stage) due to the lower amount of flame images captured for the outside set-up (design phase). Five, seven, and eight O₂ classes were studied at a laboratory scale for each fuel blend, while only three classes were considered at a semi-industrial scale. The same methodology was followed for laboratory and semi-industrial scales, explained next.

Three ML algorithms with different characteristics were analysed: Logistic Regression (LR), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and a MultiLayer Perceptron (MLP) with a single hidden layer of a hundred neurons as an artificial neural network. The predictive models were trained, validated, and tested with the datasets of image features. The dataset of each fuel blend was randomly shuffled and split into training and test sets.

In the training set, a subset of image features was automatically selected as input. Each subset of image characteristics comprises the ten variables with the highest variance for the combustion conditions. The training set was also used to tune model hyperparameters and evaluate the performance employing nested Cross-Validation (CV). The nested CV included an outer CV of 10 folds and an inner CV of 5 folds. The training set was split again into 10 pairs of training and validation subsets for the outer CV. For each training subset, the inner CV was used to define the best hyperparameter combination. Next, the selected hyperparameters were employed to train the predictive model with the training subset and measure its accuracy in predicting the O₂ concentration for the validation subset. The accuracy was averaged for every

validation subset, providing a single value for each ML algorithm and scale, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Nested CV accuracies of the predictive models for different BFG shares (%vol.) in the fuel blend at laboratory and semi-industrial scales

BFG share (%vol.)	Laboratory predictive model			Semi-industrial (inside) predictive model		
	LR	SVM	MLP	LR	SVM	MLP
0	0.9485	0.9667	0.9600	0.9920	0.9936	0.9866
70	0.9679	0.9734	0.9693	0.9666	0.9671	0.9640
80	-	-	-	0.9970	0.9980	0.9962
100	0.7749	0.7949	0.7904	-	-	-

The nested CV accuracy of the predictive models was higher than 0.77 for all the cases and development stages, showing values higher than 0.94 for BFG shares in the fuel blend lower than 90 % vol. at both laboratory and semi-industrial scales. This accuracy was achieved even for flames with low visibility and slight combustion variations that the human eye did not perceive. The increase in accuracy for the semi-industrial scale could be explained by the complexity reduction in the classification task concerning the laboratory scale. In this work, the classification task for the semi-industrial scale may be easier due to the lower number of classes to predict, the more significant image differences between classes, or the lower maximum concentration of BFG in the fuel blend (80 instead of 100 % vol.).

The three ML algorithms achieved similar accuracies in the nested CV, with differences lower than 5%. Nevertheless, SVM reached the highest accuracy for every fuel blend. The performance of this particular ML algorithm was assessed again. Predictive models were trained with the whole training set, and their accuracy was evaluated in predicting O₂ concentration for the test set (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Test accuracies of the predictive models vs. BFG share (%vol.) in the fuel blend for laboratory and semi-industrial scales

To conclude, the defined methodology and the ML algorithms were tested for laboratory and semi-industrial scales. In addition, using ML algorithms with lower complexity (LR and SVM) did not provide significant changes in performance with respect to the MLP.

CONCLUSIONS

An advanced image system for combustion monitoring in the steel industry has been validated at laboratory and semi-industrial scales. The system's robustness has been assessed by analysing results along the design, development, and implementation stages, identifying condition changes between them. The relationships between combustion conditions, flame images, image features, and performance of predictive models were analysed.

Colour cameras were proven as reliable sensors for monitoring BFG combustion on laboratory and semi-industrial scales, and the simulation of the furnace view was also accurate. For both scales, extracted image features were affected by combustion conditions, and the statistical and textural features provided adequate descriptors of the combustion for images with high and low flame visibility. The predictive models generally achieved accuracy higher than 0.95, with 0.79 as the minimum. The defined methodology was adequate for the two scales, and using ML algorithms with lower and higher capacities did not achieve relevant performance differences. The image processing and predictive models enabled the monitoring of flames with low visibility and slight combustion variations that the human eye did not perceive in the images. In summary, the imaging system was robust and overcame condition changes along the development stages, including scale (lab and semi-industrial), burner type (diffusion and premixed), and camera placement (outside and inside).

With this work, several research lines have been opened for future studies. The monitoring system could be enhanced by simultaneously supervising several burners within the same

image. In addition, experimental campaigns at an industrial scale could be performed to increase the technological readiness of the system for the industry.

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NOMENCLATURE

BFG – Blast Furnace Gas, CV – Cross-Validation, LR – Logistic Regression, ML – Machine Learning, MLP – MultiLayer Perceptron, NG – Natural Gas, O₂ – Oxygen, SVM – Support Vector Machine

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